

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

**THE INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT POWDER
IMPREGNATION
PROCESSES ON THE PROPERTIES OF L-SHAPED
WOVEN FABRIC REINFORCED PEEK COMPOSITES
BY HOT STAMP FORMING**

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CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

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DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

1. Introduction

L-shaped Parts

2. Experimental

The introduction of materials

The braided structure of CF3052 The rheological behavior of PEEK

Preparation of CF/PEEK composites

Preparation of L-shaped CF/PEEK composites

3. Results and Discussion

mechanical properties

defects

shape precision

Thanks!